

Energy consumption analytical modeling of NB-IoT devices for diverse IoT applications

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Abstract

Internet of things (IoT) has been employed in recent years across multiple disciplines in the Fifth Generation (5G) era. The low power consumption of the devices allows long battery lifetimes with increasing wireless coverage ranges. This paper presents a comprehensive power consumption model for battery lifetime estimation in narrowband IoT (NB-IoT), which is based on the user equipment (UE) state diagram and considers the extended discontinuous reception (eDRX) and power saving mode (PSM) mechanisms. This model has been used to simulate the effect of varying NB-IoT link parameters, covering a range of values defined in the specification, corresponding to a wide range of applications. Indeed, this study focuses on mathematical analysis of UE power consumption, mainly for NB-IoT communication applications. Repetitions, as defined in the standard, have also been considered in the analysis. Extensive simulations have been carried out to show the power of the proposed model, which provides accurate results for a wide variety of network parameters and let the network designer to select the most appropriated setup. They also show that the value of link parameters must be carefully selected to achieve a battery lifetime of more than a decade with a standard battery of 5 Wh capacity.

1. Introduction

EMERGING low power wide area network (LPWAN) technologies enable efficient battery usage and provide wide coverage ranges. Among them, SigFox and Long Range (LoRa) have attracted a lot of interest in unlicensed spectrum [1], while the Third Generation Partnership Program (3GPP) has standardized LPWANs in licensed spectrum, being the narrowband Internet of Things (NB-IoT) the most popular [2]. To address the requirements imposed by applications in today's Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem, LPWAN technologies optimize the modulation scheme or spectrum usage and simplify the network to a star topology [3],[4]. A considerable extension of the coverage range is achieved by these techniques.

One of the keys to the success of LPWANs is the extension of the useful life of devices through the intensive and intelligent use of consumption reduction mechanisms. In the case of NB-IoT, these are power saving mode (PSM) and discontinuous reception (DRX), already present in the

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legacy Long-Term Evolution (LTE) specification [5]. This extension of the useful life of devices allows their deployment in difficult accessible areas (such as remote or dangerous locations), where they accomplish their entire life cycle until the battery is completely exhausted. For an efficient use of the consumption reduction mechanisms, it is necessary to have an accurate model of the radio link, valid for a wide range of applications (e.g., intelligent transportation systems [6], smart metering [7][8], wearables [9], automotive [10][11], or freight management [12]). In [13] different IoT use cases are assimilated to certain data models that are arranged among four application families according to the requirements of battery life and range. Just as an example, for waste management, a battery life of 10 years and a link budget of 144 dB are established.

This article presents an analytical model of the NB-IoT link that estimates the energy consumption of the NB-IoT user equipment (UE), based on stochastic modeling of the traffic on the communication links. The exhaustive study of the NB-IoT time diagrams and the state diagram implemented by the UEs allows us to characterize the consumption required to carry out the four basic sequences: 1) complete tracking area update (TAU) period without message exchange, 2) message exchange while the device is active, 3) Uplink (UL) message transmission during PSM, and 4) message availability with the device in connected state. As an example, Fig. 1 shows the simplified flowchart of one of these sequences, concretely, when there is no data traffic. The effect of repetitions is integrated into the analysis to cover devices with different levels of coverage enhancement (CE), as represented in Fig. 2(a). Fig. 2(b) illustrates the three power device classes defined in the specification.

A wide range for each of the NB-IoT configuration parameters is considered in this paper, so that the results can be extrapolated to a wide variety of application fields. The discrete event simulation tool NS-3 is utilized for validation. This paper also discusses and validates some of the common approaches for IoT used in related work, mainly that considering non-intensive communication in terms of data volume and data rate.

Fig. 1. Simplified UE flowchart w/o NB-IoT data traffic.

Fig. 2. NB-IoT power and coverage: a) CE levels, b) power device classes.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: The required background is revised in Section 2. Section 3 presents a low-power state-diagram for a UE. Section 4 analyzes the radio link between UEs and the base station in terms of total power consumption. Section 5 shows simulation results, which are discussed in Section 6. Finally, some conclusions are drawn in Section 7.

2. Background

NB-IoT technology emerges to accommodate most IoT applications with static or limited mobility devices. Its most important characteristics are collected in Table 1 [14]-[17]. Although it shares the access technology with LTE for machine-type communications (LTE-M), the main differences can be found in the use of the spectrum and in the speed of transmission. When compared to LTE-M, NB-IoT uses a single transmission block (TBL), lowering the bandwidth to 180 kHz. Apart from using the LTE band, just like LTE-M, NB-IoT carriers can be placed in two other positions: in the LTE guard band and isolated in the Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) band. New narrowband channels are defined [18]: the physical random-access channel (NPRACH) that manages UE access over UL, and the physical downlink shared channel (NPDSCH) that limits the size in bits of the TBL based on the information shared in the information messages exchanged through the physical broadcast channel (NPBCH) and the physical downlink control channel (NPDCCH). Table 2 lists all NB-IoT channels and their corresponding link. Specifically, the subframe and TBL indices determine a maximum value of 2536 bits since Release 14 of the standard (Rel. 14). The same happens for the physical UL shared channel (NPUSCH), where the maximum size of the TBL grows from 1000 bits in Rel. 13 to 2536 bits in Rel. 14. In all channels, a symbol repetition mechanism is established for those devices located in remote areas or in the presence of obstacles that attenuate the propagation through the communication channel. It increases the received signal power and the probability of success [19]. Up to 128 repetitions can be done in the UL, while in the downlink (DL) this number grows to 2048. The collision control procedure in the NPRACH manages how the access to the medium is implemented in NB-IoT. In massive environments, when several nodes transmit at the same time, collisions may occur that are detected by each transmitting device, as it does not receive any acknowledgement. In that case, the device waits for a random time and the same symbols are retransmitted taking into account the established number of repetitions [20].

The optional extended DRX (eDRX) and PSM mechanisms are able to maintain a reduced energy consumption during the main phases of NB-IoT communication: network access,

periodic TAUs, data transmission and monitoring of the reception channel.

Next, these procedures are explained in more detail [14]21,22]:

- eDRX: With eDRX, those periods where the UE monitors the channel waiting for new data in reception are alternately combined with idle intervals where the device consumes less energy. For machine-type communications, device idle time is extended versus legacy LTE, with cycles up to approximately 3h. eDRX is available from Rel. 13.
- PSM: With PSM the node disables the transceiver until the expiration of the so-called extended timer and the consequent processing of the next TAU. However, the device remains connected to the access network, even if it is not accessible. The power consumption can be considerably reduced (depending on the total duration of the PSM), but, at the same time, the communication latency can significantly increase. This mode is defined from Rel. 12.

Feature	Value
Spectrum	Licensed
Frequency band	LTE bands: 1 to 5, 8, 11 to 14, 17 to 20, 25, 26, 28, 31, 66, 70, 71
Modulation	UL: Single-carrier frequency-division multiple access (SC-FDMA) DL: Orthogonal frequency-division multiple access (OFDMA)
Bandwidth	180 kHz
Data rate	Up to 250 kbps
Range	15 km
Latency	10 s
Mobility	Intracell

Table 1. NB-IoT main features.

Channel	Name	Link
NPRACH	Narrowband physical random-access channel	Uplink
NPDSCH	Narrowband physical downlink shared channel	Downlink
NPBCH	Narrowband physical broadcast channel	Downlink
NPDCCH	Narrowband physical downlink control channel	Downlink
NPUSCH	Narrowband physical uplink shared channel	Uplink

Table 2. NB-IoT channels.

Some works in the literature present models of the power consumption of the NB-IoT link between the UE and the evolution node base station (eNodeB). In [23] an analytical model is presented for maximum extended timer and active timer periods of 12 h and 1 h, respectively. The results of this model for an application dealing with the remote tracking of shared bicycles, are compared with simulation results. Devices transmit periodically an update message (17 bytes) and batteries are required to last a minimum of 2 years. An average error rate of 12% arises in the estimated power consumption when comparing the model and the results of simulations. Repetitions are not modeled. The authors of [24] add a new auxiliary state to the conventional DRX procedure for small data transmissions. Limiting the size of incoming packets serves to keep energy consumption controlled during the connected state of the UE. In this case, a semi-Markov model is used for the state transitions. The metrics used for

performance evaluation are the power saving factor (i.e., a ratio of the PSM duration to the total time elapsed between TAUs) and the average delay experienced by data packets. For some values of the NB-IoT timers, an energy saving factor of over 97% is shown.

In [20] a tractable theoretical model of power consumption in NB-IoT was presented, comprising data traffic in NPRACH, NPDSCH, NPUSCH, and NPDCCH; it was used to get information about the trade-off between power efficiency, latency, and coverage. Results show that coexistence of coverage classes strongly affects battery lifetime and communication latency for the UE. It is still necessary a more comprehensive analysis on the impacts of the number of allocated carriers to NB-IoT and the resource scheduling policy. Particle swarm optimization technique is applied in [25] to a subset of the configuration parameters in NB-IoT DL. Free degrees used for optimization are received power, number of sub-frames and length of MAC header.

Regarding some NB-IoT experiments reported in the literature, with an inter-arrival time (IAT) of 24 hours, a battery (5 Wh) lifetime of more than 20 years can be achieved [22],[26]-[29] provide a detailed discussion on the findings and limitations of the most significant early studies that empirically characterize NB-IoT performance. They tried to go beyond, with a set of comprehensive experiments and testbeds. In [27] the control plane procedure for sending UL reports is experimentally assessed. Voltage and current profiles are measured whilst the UE is connected to an eNodeB. Packets are sent every 6 min., and results show a relative error of the battery consumption between tests and the model of 21%. A similar approach based on Markov chain probabilities is presented in [28]. The authors model the traffic deterministically, according to the patterns for different verticals and from the measurements they have made with transceivers. They also extended the model to LTE-M devices. In [29], several case studies in the aircraft sector are considered with different package rates, concluding that NB-IoT is a low-power candidate for aviation. Results show that, using PSM and optimized peripherals, some IAT configurations serve to extend the battery lifetime. Moreover, authors in [30] employ both simulations results and experimental measurements to study the consumption of NB-IoT devices, comparing them with the estimates obtained during the standardization of 3GPP. Only a 10% difference is observed in the 2 commercial devices analyzed. In [31], two successful demonstrators for water management applications are developed by the authors. Simulation and experimental results show promising results on the battery life of IoT meters and sensing units by optimizing the NB-IoT combined links.

As it can be deduced from above references, the consumption of the UE is affected by the configuration of the NB-IoT link through 1) the timers negotiated between UE and the network (extended timer and active timer), 2) the data rate, 3) the UL parameters, 4) the number of established repetitions, and 5) the DL parameters. However, in the referenced previous works only the effect of some of these parameters is analyzed, and only for a limited range of values (see Table 3). Indeed, their main issue is the lack of accuracy and flexibility. Besides, most of the works are based on experimental measurement with limitations in the tune of relevant parameters. The main goal of this work is to propose a highly trustworthy and accurate framework for modeling the power consumption of NB-IoT (LTE-NB2 category), built over the detailed modeling of UE behavior. The model is flexible for different setups and simulations show its ability to estimate the energy consumption for a wide range of applications (i.e., related to traffic profiles, transmission rates, and network parameters). The authors also try to assess the parameters that mostly impact the battery lifetime. In the best knowledge of the authors, the

previous statements are not valid for the work in [28] where flexibility and applicability are also stated in the evaluation of the analytical model. However, some differences can be identified:

- Traffic profiles are deterministic according to some pre-defined IoT verticals, while in this paper a more generic stochastic model is addressed.
- UL repetitions are restricted to 32, while in this article the allowed limit of 128 is considered.
- Model is also valid for LTE-M devices, while in this work only NB-IoT nodes are characterized.

Work	[23]	[27]	[32]	This paper
Results	Analytical Simulation	Analytical Experimental	Simulation Optimization	Analytical Simulation
KPIs	Energy consumption	Energy consumption Latency	Energy consumption Latency	Energy consumption
Simulated time	25 days	-	1 day	6 months, 1 year, or battery life
NB-IoT timers	$t_{extended} \in [1, 12] h$ $t_{active} \in [0, 3600] s$ $\kappa = 1$	Undefined $t_{extended}$ $t_{active} = 120 s$ $\kappa = 4$	$t_{extended} \in [0, 3] h$ $t_{active} = 2 s$ Undefined κ	$t_{extended} \in [2 s, 200 days]$ $t_{active} \in [2 s, 3 h]$ $\kappa \in [1, 128]$
UL Parameters	$N_{Rep}^{UL} = 1$ $N_{Seg}^{UL} = 1$ Undefined T_{RU}^{UL}	$N_{Rep}^{UL} \in [1, 64]$ $N_{Seg}^{UL} = 1$ $T_{RU}^{UL} \in [1, 32] ms$	$N_{Rep}^{UL} = 32$ $N_{Seg}^{UL} = 1$ Undefined T_{RU}^{UL}	$N_{Rep}^{UL} \in [1, 128]$ $N_{Seg}^{UL} \in [1, 10]$ $T_{RU}^{UL} \in [1, 32] ms$
Message rate	$IAT = 24 h$ 53 B	$IAT = 6 min, 24 h$ 50 B	$IAT < 1 s$ (massive environment)	$IAT \in [5 min, 12 h]$ 300 B
DL Parameters	Not considered	Not considered	Not considered	$N_{Rep}^{DL} \in [1, 2048]$ $N_{Seg}^{DL} \in [1, 10]$

Table 3. Comparison between this NB-IoT model and references in the literature.

3. NB-IoT UE state diagram

Fig. 3 illustrates the behavior of the UE over time with the eDRX and PSM mechanisms active. Upon transmission of the periodic TAU, paging occasions (PO) are attended in each of the DRX cycles until the timers expire after t_{inact} and t_{act} seconds, respectively. The UE has no control over the inactivity timer, as its period is set by the network. Conversely, the active timer is negotiated between both parties as follows: the UE reports the desired period value in the connection request and the network responds with a confirmation according to the settings it supports. Once the device is in PSM, it remains in deep sleep until the expiration of the extended timer (in t_{ext} seconds). Then the next TAU is launched. The possible periods of the extended timer and the active timer are shown in (1) and (2), respectively, in a matricial way [32][33]. They are formatted according to "GPRS Timer 3" and "GPRS Timer 2" elements, respectively.

Fig. 3. Power levels and timeline of an NB-IoT UE: a) receiving MT configuration data at one eDRX cycle, b) sending MO data acquired from sensors after UL grant.

$$t_{ext} = \begin{pmatrix} 2 \text{ s.} & 4 \text{ s.} & \dots & 1 \text{ min. } 2 \text{ s.} \\ 30 \text{ s.} & 1 \text{ min.} & \dots & 15 \text{ min. } 30 \text{ s.} \\ 1 \text{ min.} & 2 \text{ min.} & \dots & 31 \text{ min.} \\ 10 \text{ min.} & 20 \text{ min.} & \dots & 5 \text{ h. } 10 \text{ min.} \\ 1 \text{ h.} & 2 \text{ h.} & \dots & 31 \text{ h.} \\ 10 \text{ h.} & 20 \text{ h.} & \dots & 12 \text{ d. } 22 \text{ h.} \\ 13 \text{ d. } 8 \text{ h.} & 26 \text{ d. } 16 \text{ h.} & \dots & 413 \text{ d. } 8 \text{ h.} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$t_{act} = \begin{pmatrix} 2 \text{ s.} & 4 \text{ s.} & \dots & 1 \text{ min. } 2 \text{ s.} \\ 1 \text{ min.} & 2 \text{ min.} & \dots & 31 \text{ min.} \\ 6 \text{ min.} & 12 \text{ min.} & \dots & 3 \text{ h. } 6 \text{ min.} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The eDRX cycles can contain several paging time windows (PTW) relative to each PO performed during the cycle. The duration of an eDRX cycle and of a PTW are defined by [34]:

$$t_{eDRX} = 2^i * 10.24 \text{ s}; \quad i = 1, \dots, 10 \quad (3)$$

$$PTW = 2i * 1.28 \text{ s}; \quad i = 1, \dots, 16 \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3(a) illustrates the case when the UE reports that some data is available in DL after monitoring the NPDCCH in one of the eDRX cycles.

Then, the transmission procedure of the master- (MIB) and system- (SIB) information blocks

are initiated. The device is still in radio resource control (RRC) Idle state. After the transmission of the preamble that initiates the exchange of random-access (RA) messages, the UE switches to RRC Connected state and receives the mobile terminated (MT) data (e.g., sensor setup information) through NPDSCH. At the end of reception, the device remains connected until the inactivity timer expires. Fig. 3(b) shows the behavior of the UE discussed above until it has a sensor measurement available to transmit in the UL direction. While in PSM, synchronization, RA, and connection request procedures are initiated after the reception of the UL grant. Once in RRC Connected state, the device transmits the mobile originated (MO) data using NPUSCH. Fig. 4 shows the operating state diagram of a UE, according to the temporal characterization shown above. Note that synchronization messages, the RA procedure, and the request for an RRC connection are simplified to a unique state. It is noticeable that different sequences occur iteratively according to the events of timer expiration (dashed lines) or the availability of messages in one of the link directions between the device and the eNodeB (continuous lines). Specifically, there are four sequences that can be extracted from the diagram:

- *Sequence A*: Time elapsed between TAUs without the reception of any packet. The device does not receive notification of any message available in UL or DL during the period of inactivity and extended timers. In this case, the time elapsed between messages in both directions of communication is necessarily longer than the extended timer. The probability of occurrence of this sequence combines the probability of not receiving any message after t_{act} seconds while the device is active in RRC Idle, with the probability of not receiving packets at the end of the t_{ext} interval.
- *Sequence B*: DL notification or UL grant with the device active. The device goes to RRC Idle after the inactivity timer expiration. Once there, in Idle state, the notification of any message available in the UL or DL occurs. The latter case is the one represented in Fig. 3(a). Therefore, the probability of occurrence for this sequence corresponds to that of having some message in an interval smaller than t_{act} seconds.
- *Sequence C*: UL message availability with device in deep sleep. The device in RRC Idle goes to PSM when the active timer expires. While asleep, there is no option to receive any DL messages, but UL message indications are attended. When the UE is reconnected, the corresponding packet is then transmitted. Fig. 3(b) corresponds to this sequence. Here, the probability of occurrence is associated to the case where no data is received in the t_{act} period, but a UL grant is notified before the extended timer expires.
- *Sequence D*: DL or UL message arrival with the device connected. Now, a message arrives while the device is in RRC Connected. This will normally occur when the packet IAT is smaller than the period of the inactivity timer. The probability of its occurrence is, in turn, linked to the reception of some data in a time shorter than the inactivity period.

4. NB-IoT power consumption: proposed analytical model

The objective of this section is the estimation of the power consumption in the UE according to the simplified state diagram of Fig. 4. Table 4 lists main parameters used in the characterization of the timing and power consumption of the sequences. In our model, both sending and receiving data flows are modeled as stochastic processes, whose characteristics are dependent

on application. UL and DL packet arrival rates (λ_{UL} and λ_{DL} , respectively) fit the Poisson distribution, so that the IAT in both links follows an exponential distribution [23][27]. Modelling the energy consumed by the UE in each of the operating sequences allows us to determine the long-term consumption of the system and to estimate battery lifetime of field devices. The study will take into account the two consumption reduction mechanisms defined in NB-IoT, as they are key to achieving many years of battery lifetime.

Fig. 4. Simplified UE flowchart w/o NB-IoT data traffic.

4.1. Probability of sequences

Let λ_{tot} be the combined rate of packet availability in both directions, UL and DL. The probability of a packet arriving in an interval (t_1, t_2) is $1 - e^{-\lambda_{tot}(t_2-t_1)}$, according to the Poisson distribution's IAT. Consequently, the expressions for the computation of the probability of each sequence are:

$$p_A = e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{inact}} e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{act}} e^{-\lambda_{tot}(t_{ext}-t_{act})} \approx e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{ext}} \quad (5)$$

$$p_B = e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{inact}} (1 - e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{act}}) \approx 1 - e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{act}} \quad (6)$$

$$p_C = e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{inact}} e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{act}} (1 - e^{-\lambda_{tot}(t_{ext}-t_{act})}) \approx e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{act}} (1 - e^{-\lambda_{tot}(t_{ext}-t_{act})}) \quad (7)$$

$$p_D = 1 - e^{-\lambda_{tot}t_{inact}} \approx 0 \quad (8)$$

Approximations in (5), (6), (7), and (8) are valid for most low-power IoT applications. With a typical data rate of only few messages per day, given that the inactivity timer has a period of at most 10.24 s (set by the standard) [35], the probability of multiple messages being serviced when the device is connected is negligible. Under these assumptions, the probability of occurrence of sequences A and B depend only on NB-IoT extended and active timers, respectively. Furthermore, Fig. 5 shows the evolution of probability of occurrence of sequence C in terms of both timer periods, as stated in (7). Without loss of generality, in this figure, λ_{UL} and λ_{DL} are assumed to be equal.

Parameter	Description
λ_{UL}	Packet rate in UL
λ_{DL}	Packet rate in DL
t_{inact}	Period of the inactivity timer (in seconds)
t_{ext}	Period of the extended timer (in seconds)
t_{act}	Period of the active timer (in seconds)
p_x	Probability of sequence x , where $x \in \{A, B, C\}$
T_x	Mean duration of sequence x , where $x \in \{A, B, C\}$
E_x	Mean energy consumption for sequence x , where $x \in \{A, B, C\}$
T_{seq}	Mean sequence duration
E_{seq}	Mean energy consumption required for a sequence
P_{TAU}	Power consumption during TAU processing
P_{idle}	Power consumption during DRX Idle state
P_{pg}	Power consumption during PO monitoring
P_{PSM}	Power consumption during PSM
T^{RA}	Duration of synchronization, random access, and RRC connection request
T^{UL}	Mean duration of UL transmission
T^{DL}	Mean duration of DL reception
T_B^{Msg}	Generic indicator of the time required to handle a message in either direction during sequence B
P_{RA}	Power consumed by synchronization procedure, random access, and RRC connection request.
P_{Tx}	Power consumption during UL transmission
P_{Rx}	Power consumption during DL reception
t_{PSM}	Maximum time interval that the UE can remain at PSM

Table 4. Model parameters for consumption estimation.

It can be observed in above equations that there is a set of timer periods with a predominant sequence ($p_i \approx 1$) while the probabilities for the other sequences are negligible. For example, sequence C predominates for (1 packet/h, $t_{ext} = 10$ h, $t_{act} = 1$ min.), while sequence A predominates with (1 packet/day, $t_{ext} = 15$ min., $t_{act} = 6$ min.). In other cases, the sequences occur with more evenly distributed probabilities, as it is the case with (10 packets/day, $t_{ext} = 1$ h, $t_{act} = 36$ min.). Moreover, as IAT decreases, sequence B becomes more likely to occur and, at the same time, sequence A is less probable.

Parameter	Description
t_{eDRX}	eDRX cycle (in seconds)
PTW	Paging time window (in seconds)
κ	Number of windows per cycle
μ	Number of eDRX cycles in Idle state

Table 5. Notation of eDRX parameters.

Parameter	Description
DCI	DL control information
MCS	Modulation and coding scheme
$TBS_{DL/UL}$	transmission block size (in bits)
I_{SF}	Subframe indication field
N_{SF}	Number of subframes in NPDSCH
t_{SF}	Subframe time
I_{RU}	Resource unit indication field
N_{RU}	Number of resource units in NPUSCH
t_{slot}	Slot time
N_{slots}^{UL}	Number of slots in UL
L_{DL}	Protocol data unit length in DL
L_{UL}	Protocol data unit length in UL
$HMAC$	Size of the medium access control headers (in bits)

Table 6. Notation of parameters affecting UL/DL packet duration.

Fig. 5. Probability of sequence C against the periods of extended and active timers: a) for a rate of 1 packet per day in UL and DL, b) for a rate of 1 packet per hour in UL and DL.

4.2. Battery lifetime estimation

Tables 5 and 6 include the notation of extra parameters related to eDRX cycles and the duration of UL/DL packet transmissions, respectively. Starting with sequence A, the duration of each cycle consists of transmitting the TAU with a fixed duration, t_{TAU} , plus the full period of active and extended timers. Let $\mu = t_{act}/t_{eDRX}$ be the number of eDRX cycles in Idle state and $\kappa = t_{eDRX}/PTW$ be the number of windows occurring in each cycle. On average, the duration of

sequence A and its power consumption are given by:

$$T_A = t_{TAU} + t_{inact} + t_{act} + (t_{ext} - t_{act}) = t_{TAU} + t_{inact} + t_{ext} \quad (9)$$

$$E_A = t_{TAU}P_{TAU} + (t_{act} + t_{inact})P_{idle} + \kappa(\mu + 1)P_{pg} + (t_{ext} - t_{act})P_{PSM} \quad (10)$$

A device not reaching PSM is representative of sequence B. The probability that UL or DL messages arrive in the i -th eDRX cycle ($i \leq \mu$), while the device is in Idle state, must be calculated [23]. This is, the combined probability that a UL-type packet arrives earlier (or a DL-type packet in the complementary case), $p_{B,UL}$, and that this message is available in one of the discontinuous reception cycles, $p_{B,UL}^{idle}$. These expressions are given by:

$$p_{B,UL} = \frac{1}{p_B} \int_0^{t_{act}} \lambda_{UL} e^{-\lambda_{tot}t} dt = \frac{\lambda_{UL}}{\lambda_{tot}} \quad (11)$$

$$p_{B,UL}^{idle} = p_{B,UL} \frac{1}{1 - e^{-\lambda_{UL}t_{active}}} \int_{t_{eDRX}}^{(i+1)t_{eDRX}} \lambda_{UL} e^{-\lambda_{UL}t} dt = p_{B,UL} \frac{e^{-\lambda_{UL}t_{eDRX}} - e^{-\lambda_{UL}(i+1)t_{eDRX}}}{1 - e^{-\lambda_{UL}t_{act}}} \quad (12)$$

$$p_{B,DL} = \frac{\lambda_{DL}}{\lambda_{tot}} \quad (13)$$

$$p_{B,DL}^{idle} = p_{B,DL} \frac{e^{-\lambda_{DL}t_{eDRX}} - e^{-\lambda_{DL}(i+1)t_{eDRX}}}{1 - e^{-\lambda_{DL}t_{act}}} \quad (14)$$

Then, the average duration of sequence B while a UE is connected, T_B^{idle} , and the average consumed energy, E_B^{idle} , are calculated as:

$$T_B^{idle} = \sum_{i=0}^{\mu-1} [(i + 0.5)t_{eDRX}p_{B,UL}^{idle} + (i + 1)t_{eDRX}p_{B,DL}^{idle}] \quad (15)$$

$$E_B^{idle} = \sum_{i=0}^{\mu-1} \left[(i + 1) \left((P_{pg} + 0.5t_{eDRX}P_{idle})p_{B,UL}^{idle} + (P_{pg} + t_{eDRX}P_{idle})p_{B,DL}^{idle} \right) \right] \quad (16)$$

Without loss of generality, the PO is located at the end of the eDRX cycle. UL grant, on the other hand, can be received at any instant of the interval so that, on average, it may be quantified in the middle. In this way, we can obtain the average values of the interval duration of B sequence and of the energy consumed:

$$T_B = t_{inact} + T_B^{idle} + T^{RA} + T_B^{Msg} \quad (17)$$

$$E_B = \begin{cases} t_{inact}P_{idle} + E_B^{idle} + T^{RA}P_{RA} + T^{UL}P_{Tx}, & \text{for a UL message} \\ t_{inact}P_{idle} + E_B^{idle} + T^{RA}P_{RA} + T^{DL}P_{Rx}, & \text{for a DL message} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

T^{RA} and P_{RA} depend on control plane (mandatory in NB-IoT specification) and user plane (optional for NB-IoT) optimizations applied in the communication between UE and eNodeB, since these optimizations influence the number of messages exchanged in the random access (RA) and connection request phases [36]. In fact, the service request (SR) procedure of legacy LTE generally requires higher consumption and implies a longer duration for those phases. Computation for control plane optimizations is detailed in [27]. Further research efforts must be made in the case that the optional user plane optimizations are active.

Sequence C implies the arrival of some message, necessarily on UL, while the UE is in PSM

state. Let $t_{PSM} = t_{extended} - t_{active}$ be the maximum period at PSM. The entire active timer period is consumed, but the time the device remains in PSM (T_C^{PSM}) depends on the instant when UL packet is available. On average:

$$T_C^{PSM} = \int_0^{t_{PSM}} \frac{t \cdot \lambda_{UL} e^{-\lambda_{UL} t}}{1 - e^{-\lambda_{UL} t_{PSM}}} dt = \frac{1}{\lambda_{UL}} - \frac{t_{PSM} e^{-\lambda_{UL} t_{PSM}}}{1 - e^{-\lambda_{UL} t_{PSM}}} \quad (19)$$

With UL grant, the device employs a period equal to that of sequence B to reconnect and send data to the network. Consequently, by averaging the time interval and the energy required for this third sequence, the following equations are obtained:

$$T_C = t_{inact} + t_{act} + T_C^{PSM} + T^{RA} + T^{UL} \quad (20)$$

$$E_C = (t_{act} + t_{inact})P_{idle} + \kappa(\mu + 1)P_{pg} + T_C^{PSM}P_{PSM} + T^{RA}P_{RA} + T^{UL}P_{Tx} \quad (21)$$

In sequences B and C, both DL or UL communication affect the average duration and consumption. To determine to what extent the result is affected, resource allocation data contained in the DL control information (DCI) received by the UE in the paging procedure or via UL grant, as described in [19], must be analyzed. In NPDSCH, for each TBL, or segment, N consecutive subframes are used, as it is set in the corresponding DCI fields. The subframe indication field, I_{SF} , and the modulation and coding scheme (MCS) set the TBL size (TBS) between 2 and 85 bytes on DL (as of Rel. 14, in the LTE-NB2 specification, an upper maximum TBS of $317 B$ is set for both communication directions [37]). The number of subframes, N_{SF} , can vary between 1 and 10. Assuming no repetitions ($N_{Rep} = 1$), the number of subframes allows to obtain the duration of each TBL as the product of N_{SF} and the subframe time (on DL, $t_{SF} = 1 ms$), up to a maximum of $10 ms$. Thus, for a protocol data unit length of L_{DL} bits, $T^{DL} = \lceil L_{DL} / (TBS_{DL}(MCS, I_{SF}) - H_{MAC}) \rceil \cdot N_{SF} \cdot t_{SF}$, where H_{MAC} is the size of the medium access control (MAC) headers.

A similar analysis is applicable to NPUSCH. N consecutive subframes are again employed. TBS is given by MCS and the resource unit (RU) indication field, I_{RU} , of the DCI in UL grant. I_{RU} defines the number of RUs (N_{RU}), which can vary between 1 and 10. In this case, the upper limit for the TBS is $125 B$ at Rel. 13 and increases to 317 bytes since Rel. 14. Without repetitions, $N = N_{RU} N_{slots}^{UL}$, being N_{slots}^{UL} the number of NB-IoT slots in the UL of each RU. Each slot consists of 7 Single-carrier frequency division multiple access (SC-FDMA) symbols. N_{slots}^{UL} is given by the number of carriers used (1, 3, 6 or 12 tones) and by frequency spacing (Δf) of 3.75 or 15 kHz. The duration of each segment can reach, here, up to $320 ms$. With L_{UL} being the protocol data unit size (in bits) on UL, the transmission duration is $T^{UL} = \lceil L_{UL} / (TBS_{UL}(MCS, I_{SF}) - H_{MAC}) \rceil \cdot N_{RU} \cdot N_{slots}^{UL} \cdot t_{slot}$. Time slot, t_{slot} , is inversely proportional to Δf (i.e., $0.5 ms$ for 15 kHz and $2 ms$ for 3.75 kHz).

Once each type of sequence has been analyzed separately, the required duration and consumption per sequence is averaged considering the individual probabilities of sequences A, B and C:

$$T_{seq} = p_A T_A + p_B T_B + p_C T_C \quad (22)$$

$$E_{seq} = p_A E_A + p_B E_B + p_C E_C \quad (23)$$

$$P_{seq} = \frac{E_{seq}}{T_{seq}} \quad (24)$$

where P_{seq} represents the average power required to complete a sequence. This value helps estimating the depletion of battery, since it refers to the average consumption required for the state machine completion, regardless of the sequence taking place. In this work, battery degradation over the time is not considered.

4.3. The effect of repetitions

Repetitions defined in NB-IoT specification directly influence the duration of T^{RA} , T^{DL} , and T^{UL} . Remember that three different CE levels may be established during initialization. Hereafter, this repetition mechanism is described. It consists of repeating transmitted symbols a previously established number of times, so that the signal-to-noise ratio at receiver side is raised. Each NB-IoT channel admits its own configuration of this number of repetitions. Further details can be found in [38]-[41]. The preamble sent by the UE consists of four symbol groups that are repeated up to 128 times. A symbol group is the composition of five symbols: a cyclic prefix and four equal symbols. The NPRACH uses the 3.75 kHz frequency spacing, so there are 48 subcarriers available in the 180 kHz BW. These subcarriers are distributed over the network among the defined CE levels, up to a maximum of three, in blocks of twelve subcarriers. When transmitting the preamble, the UE randomly selects the subcarrier among those available for its CE level and sends the first group of symbols. Thereafter, according to a predefined frequency hopping pattern, the preamble is sent on the corresponding subcarriers [35]. Repetitions should not be confused with the retransmission mechanism that occurs at MAC layer when collisions occur between different UEs [38]. Only upon detection of the collision, a random back off is initiated and the same message is retransmitted [40].

Of course, the retransmission includes all repetitions according to the CE level of the device. It is used to decrease the block error rate in massive environments. Table 7 shows the maximum increase in duration according to the possible configurations of repetitions in the NPDSCH and NPUSCH channels [19].

Channel	Num. of Repetitions	Frequency Spacing (kHz)	Max. TBL time w/o repetitions (ms)	Max. TBL time with repetitions (ms)
NPDSCH	1-2048	15, 12 tones	10	20480
		3.75, 1 tone	320	40960
		15, 1 tone	80	10240
NPUSCH	1-128	15, 3 tones	40	5120
		15, 6 tones	20	2560
		15, 12 tones	10	1280

Table 7. Maximum TBL duration with and w/o repetitions.

5. Simulation results

NB-IoT radio link characterization allows consolidating the knowledge of this recent technology and serves to fully analyze the proper configuration to accomplish the requirements of the IoT application under consideration. Power values required for main operations are given in Table 8. They have been obtained experimentally using a wireless transceiver of SARA-N3 family from the manufacturer u-blox [42], with NB-IoT coverage. They are used as input parameters in the model of Section 4, employing NS-3 for discrete event simulations. In the scope of this paper, the “lte” module is modified to comply with Rel. 13 and Rel. 14 of the NB-IoT specification. Note that for each case under interest, 500 iterations are sequenced through Monte Carlo simulations. Let us consider two traffic scenarios in simulations: 1) One packet every day in each communication link (low data rate for non-intense IoT applications) and 2) one packet every hour in each communication link (higher data rate for more intense IoT use cases). Again, the number of packets sent by UL and DL are considered equal. Table 9 summarizes input values employed in simulations for NB-IoT timers, UL configuration, and DL setup.

Power parameter	Value
P_{idle}	21 mW
P_{RA}	464 mW
P_{Tx}	716 mW
P_{Rx}	213 mW
P_{PSM}	15 μ W

Table 8. Experimental simulation inputs: Power consumption.

Results are presented as a function of the estimated battery lifetime in years, obtained as the ratio between the nominal capacity of the battery (5 Wh) and the annual consumption of the device in Wh.

Parameter	Values
t_{inact}	10 s
t_{ext}	[2 s, 200 days], see (1)
t_{act}	[2 s, 3 h], see (2)
κ	{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128}
Num. of repetitions (UL)	{1, 2, 5, 10, 24, 50, 64, 75, 90, 128}
Num. of segments (UL)	{1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10}
RU duration in ms (UL)	{1, 2, 4, 8, 32}
Num. of repetitions (DL)	{1, 10, 128, 256, 500, 650, 800, 1024, 1250, 1650, 1800, 2048}
Num. of segments (DL)	{1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10}

Table 9. Simulation inputs: NB-IoT timers and UL/DL parameters

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 6. UE's battery lifetime estimation as a function of NB-IoT timers and data rate, w/o repetitions: (a) Extended timer, (b) Active timer, (c) κ parameter, (d) number of daily packets in each link.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 7. UE's battery lifetime estimation as a function of UL and DL configuration, with and w/o repetitions: (a) UL repetitions, (b) UL segments, (c) RU duration, (d) DL repetitions.

Fig. 6 illustrates UE battery life estimation relative to NB-IoT timers, from (22)-(24). Specifically, Fig. 6(a) and 6(b) contemplate the full range of possible values of extended timer and active timer, respectively. The influence of parameter κ is shown in Fig. 6(c) using the following configuration of timers: $t_{active} = 22\text{ s}$ and $t_{extended} = 15\text{ h}$. Recall that this value represents the number of paging windows per cycle. It is observed that κ affects device lifetime to a lesser extent than the periods of timers. In fact, with typical values of this parameter ($\kappa < 8$), the energy increase keeps small. Energy required per cycle grows inversely with the value of t_{active} . If extended timer exceeds the period between packets, battery life stabilizes, since in these cases the C-cycle predominates in operation. Battery is reduced by about half for $t_{extended} = 15\text{ h}$. If the timer becomes shorter, lifetime decreases considerably. In the case of t_{active} , battery life decreases for values greater than 60 s. 3GPP requirement about a lifetime of the battery longer than 10 years is met only with certain configurations. Number of exchanged packets per day is another important parameter, as it is also usually defined by the type of IoT application. Fig. 6(d) indicates the decreasing trend of battery life as the message rate increases. Again, without loss of generality, the number of packets sent by UL and DL are considered equal and the same configuration of timers as in Fig. 6(c).

The dependency of UL and DL parameters is shown in Fig- 7. Referring to UL configuration, in terms of packets transmitted by the UE and spectral utilization, it can also affect the energy consumption of this link and, consequently, the level of discharge of device's battery. These are the number of repetitions (N_{Rep}^{UL}), the number of segments (N_{Seg}^{UL}), and the duration of each RU (T_{RU}^{UL}). The latter has a moderate impact on the power consumption of the UE. In the presence of repetitions, with $N_{Rep}^{UL} = 8$, the highest energy consumed reaches around 8 J, while the minimum is 4.21 J using a single tone. Otherwise, the number of repetitions in the UL strongly affects the UE consumption (Fig. 7(a)). For the maximum value of this parameter, $N_{Rep}^{UL} = 128$, battery lifetime is less than 1 year. The number of UL segments only slightly affects battery lifetime, as shown in Fig. 7(b). Energy increase does not reach 18% in any case. On the other hand, RU duration in UL moderately affects the energy consumption of the battery (Fig. 7(c)). Neither the number of DL repetitions (which can be up to 2048), illustrated in Fig. 7(d), nor the number of segments, not shown in Fig. 7, have any influence on battery lifetime. Also note that on DL, subframe duration is always equal to 1 ms (12 tones).

6. Discussion

Estimating UE's energy consumption is a necessary preliminary step for the design of low-power diverse IoT systems. Given results remark that it is possible to achieve an objective of a battery life of more than 10 years when the network parameters are properly chosen. A comparison between this paper and other works in the literature is given in Table 3. It lists the goals of each work, time range covered by simulations, and values of input parameters considered in each case. It is observed that those references showing simulation results, [23] and [32], use a simulation interval much lower than the one used in this paper. In all cases, packet transmission and reception are modeled according to Poisson distributions and the IAT as another stochastic process following an exponential distribution. In addition, in this article the analysis of the influence of NB-IoT parameters on results is more exhaustive in the 4 defined categories: 1) NB-IoT timers, 2) UL parameters, 3) data rate, and 4) DL parameters. Full available ranges are considered.

Note that Fig. 6 and 7 bring the results of simulations averaging the values obtained in the 500 MonteCarlo iterations (see Section 5). The number of iterations was established as a trade-off between simulation time and accuracy. In all cases, the accuracy of the model against simulations remains higher than 90%. In some cases, a higher accuracy would be gotten if a higher number of iterations was set (i.e., with important increments of running time)

For a fair comparison with [23] and [27], the IAT has to be similar, since the message rate is double in this paper for the assumption of non-intensive IoT communications. Under these conditions, applying an IAT = 24 h, it is found that obtained results are quite comparable. Maximum battery lifetime without repetitions is 26.41 years in the proposed model, while 28 years and 22.5 years are provided by [23] and [27], respectively. The dependence of energy consumption with repetitions on UL in [27], obtained experimentally, provides similar results to those of the model illustrated here. As $N_{\text{Rep}}^{\text{UL}}$ grows, the variation between the two results becomes smaller. In fact, with $N_{\text{Rep}}^{\text{UL}} = 64$, only a 2.57% difference is observable. Then, model faithfully represents the experimental measurements carried out by the authors in [27] and, additionally, extends the set of values of repetitions to the maximum it can take ($N_{\text{Rep}}^{\text{UL}} = 128$). Similarly, in [23], a trend for the battery life with respect to NB-IoT timers analogous to the one presented in this model is shown. Some differences appear in the values due to packet size, battery safety margin, and time range. Related to [32], authors build a multi-objective optimization model with a cost function dependent on the energy consumed by the UEs and communication delay. By using weights, they aim to minimize the energy expenditure and latency. An application of massive machine-type communication for IoT is considered. As a result, the behavior of the optimization algorithm is simulated for a densely populated network (twice as many devices as total available mobile resources), in which the following objectives are pursued: 1) Battery lifetime of 10 years and 2) delay less than 1 s. Although this is a very different perspective from the model in this paper, it is possible to draw an analogy by using the latter for the discrimination of those link configurations that provide a battery life of more than a decade. Finally, modeling communication latency was not part of this work, and it would be considered in the future.

7. Conclusion

This paper contains the mathematical analysis of the UE power consumption in the framework of IoT applications. A general approach requires considering extreme ranges for the NB-IoT communication. The results are obtained based on a simplified state diagram of the device, and a probabilistic model of the sequences derived from the transitions between states. The procedure consists of four systematic steps: 1) calculation of the probability of occurrence of each sequence, 2) calculation of the average duration and energy consumed of each sequence, 3) obtention of the average power per sequence, and 4) estimation of the battery lifetime. Simulations show that the parameters that most strongly affect the consumption in the NB-IoT link are the extended timer, the active timer, the message rate, the repetitions occurring in the UL, the number of segments in the UL, and the duration of the RUs. With an IAT=12 h and a proper configuration of the rest of parameters, the battery lifetime is over 11 years. The estimated consumption is consistent with other analytical and experimental models in the literature but including a general model that takes into account the most significant parameters of an NB-IoT link. This model is of much help for network designers in the selection of the most suitable link parameters.

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